

Mapping the Research Profile of Prof. Mohammad Abdulkader Akbarsha: A Scientometric Approach

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Abstract

The research publications of Prof. Mohammad Abdulkader, Akbarsha, a Scientist of Life Sciences, were quantitatively and qualitatively analyzed in this study. His first paper was published in 1992 when he was working in the School of Life Sciences, Bharathidasan University. His 184 research papers cover research topics in Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology (82); Chemistry (46); Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics (40); Agricultural and Biological Sciences (39); Medicine (25); Health Professions (15); Chemical Engineering (14);

Material Science (12); Multidisciplinary (10); Physics and Astronomy (9); Environmental Science (6); Immunology and Microbiology (5); and so on. Many of his research publications are done in collaboration with scientists from abroad, Saudi Arabia (42); United States (16); France and Singapore (6); Switzerland (5); Finland, Germany, Italy, Spain and Taiwan (3); Hong Kong and South Korea (2); 6 countries each (1). He collaborated with 331 researchers and recorded 4368 Citations (5639 Cited References), (H-Index-34), (4734 citations in Google Scholar). His research productivity and quality are of an order that can inspire the young researchers/scientists and he can be considered as a "role model scientist to emulate" in the field of Life Sciences.

Keywords: Scientometric Approach; Bibliometric; Citations; Highly Cited Papers

INTRODUCTION

Most Scientific and technological activities in India are funded directly and/or indirectly, from the public money, and virtually all scientists and technologists today are salaried people or hold fellowships. This calls for a continues assessment of performance both of the individual scientists, technologists and of the institutions, thus ensuring that neither the scientist, the technologist nor the administrative structure get stratified and therefore, fossilized.

Scientometrics provides an understating of the structure of the scientific activity, subject disciplines being researched, institutions involved, strengths in the scientific groups and their communication/outlet channels. Scientometrics is an application of quantitative methods to the history of science/scientists (Kalyane, 1995). In recent years, we have used scientometric tools in order to assess the quantitative analysis of many scientific research fields such as pheromone biology (Rajagopal et al., 2013), yoga research (Poornima and Surulinathi, 2019), Indian contribution to drugs discovery (Sankaralingam et al., 2020), global research output of COVID-19 (Surulinathi et al., 2020) etc. It is one of the techniques for documenting and collating works of eminent scientists and researchers. In this paper, we present a concise sketch of Prof. Mohammad Abdulkader Akbarsha, (Scopus Author ID: 7003760724) stressing on his scientific achievements. His research has had a great impact in the fields dealing with Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology, Chemistry, Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics, Agricultural and Biological Sciences, Medicine, Chemical Engineering, Material Science, Health Professions, Physics and Astronomy, Environmental Science, Immunology and Microbiology, Engineering, Energy, Mathematics, Nursing, Computer Science and Veterinary.

M. A. Akbarsha – Scientist of Modern Life Science:

His independent research, though started at Jamal Mohamed College, Tiruchirappalli, has been mostly at Bharathidasan University which he moved into in 1989, where he was working in the School of Life Sciences. He started University career as a Reader, then Professor of Animal Science and Biomedical Science, Co-ordinator of the School, with 7 departments, and then Dean- Faculty of Science. He superannuated in June 2008, and immediately became Emeritus Professor of Life Sciences. Within a year he was invited by Doerenkamp-Zbinden Foundation, with the support of a huge grant, to work for popularizing alternatives to animal experiments in India, which he started in 2009 and the tenure was over in 2017. Thereafter, he is working as Honorary Research Coordinator in National College, Tiruchirappalli. His research endeavor started in 1974, and continues to date. Areas his of research include Endocrinology, Reproductive Biology, Phytotherapy, Cancer Biology, Obesity, *In Vivo & In Vitro* Toxicology, Alternatives to Animal Experiments, with great emphasis on histological, ultrastructural and molecular biology tools. More than 280 research/review publications in peer-reviewed journals, out of which 130 are listed in the NCBI-PubMed; and more than 180 in Scopus. A few appeared in RSC and ACS Journals. Full coverage could be found in Science Direct, Research Gate, etc. He authored more than 15 review chapters in international edited publications. He is Editor-in-Chief of *Journal of Endocrinology and Reproduction since 2006*, the official organ of the Society for Reproductive Biology and Comparative Endocrinology, India, the Society for which he was President for 2 years, 2008-2010. He Co-authored of two books on *Indian Medicinal Plants* and has two international

patents and quite a few gene bank submissions. He attended more than 300 seminars / symposia / conferences and presented papers / chaired sessions / delivered key-note addresses. Twenty-three candidates have been awarded Ph.D., under his direct guidance, and he has been co-guide to many more candidates. He has operated several sponsored projects (UGC, DST, CSIR, ICMR) and has been awarded grants for international collaborative studies, including from NIH-USA and Koman Breast Foundation, USA and Doerenkamp-Zbinden Foundation, Switzerland. He was conferred Peranaidu Govindarajulu Gold Medal Oration award of Society for Reproductive Biology and Comparative Endocrinology, in 2016. He has also been conferred several other recognitions and awards including more than 20 travel awards to attend international conferences. Thus, he has visited countries such as Australia, Norway, UK, USA, Germany, Italy, France, Ethiopia, Saudi Arabia, Sri Lanka, Canada, Czech Republic, Japan, Brazil and Finland, some of these countries twice or more. He is best known for research collaborations, within India and abroad.

Service Organizations, University Grants Commission (UGC), Ministry of Environment and Forests (MoEF), and Medical & Pharmacy Councils, had raised concerns about the use of animals in learning and research. In this backdrop, Prof. M. A. Akbarsha, established the Mahatma Gandhi – Doerenkamp Center (MGDC) for Alternatives to Use of Animals in Life Science Education in 2009 at Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, for which he received a grant from Doerenkamp-Zbinden Foundation (DZF), Switzerland. He was Director of the Center and also Gandhi-Gruber- Doerenkamp Chair, an endowed Chair of the DZF. The center played a pivotal role in changing the attitude of students, teachers and research community towards the alternatives to use of animals in academics and research. The standalone facility of MGDC specialized in three domains viz., in vitro, in silico and alternative model organisms, each domain conducting research, training and outreach programs to overall achieve the vision of making India as a leader in modern tools of learning and research. The tenure of the grant was over in 2016, when in order to continue the brilliance of the center, the university proposed to expand the activity of MGDC by bringing the expertise of faculties from various departments to enrich its multi-disciplinary activities. The idea of establishment of a national facility named National Centre for Alternatives to Animal Experiments (NCAAE) was approved and funded by the UGC under CPEPA (Centre with Potential for Excellence in Particular Area) scheme. The main aim of this Centre is to promote excellence in education by launching modern tools in the field of alternatives to animal experiments. The primary focus of NCAAE is to establish the country as a leader on par with International Institutes in Human Science by adopting alternative methods to animal experiments. Since the tenure of DZF fund was over Prof. Akbarsha had to leave the University, and he joined the National College as Research Co-ordinator, on invitation, which assignment he still continues. In this role he helps the faculty in conducting quality research, writing effective proposals for availing grants from funding agencies, writing technically sound research articles for publication in reputed journals. He also continues his own research collaborations and engages in research and publication.

OBJECTIVES

- To analyze the Author Productivity;
- To identify the Domain-wise contribution;
- To identify the Channels of publications;
- To analyze the Research collaboration of Author, Institutions and Country;
- To identify the Funding Sponsors for his research;
- To analyze the Citations and Publications Impact;
- To identify the highly Cited Papers and
- To identify the year-wise distribution of publications.

METHODOLOGY

A complete bibliography of his research publications from 1992–2020 has been catalogued and standard bibliometric fields was analyzed by normal count procedure for various domains such as author Citations, Collaboration Institutions, Countries, Authors, Funding Source and Subject domains. The data was downloaded from Scopus database, with the search string “Mohammad Abdulkader Akbarsha” with author field.

Figure: 1. Citation Profile of Prof. M.A. Akbarsha

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the period, Professor published 184 research publications. Details of International Collaboration, domain-wise contribution, Channels of communication, Author and Institutional collaboration, Funding sponsors, and highly cited papers are highlighted quantitatively.

International collaboration:

The publications cover a total of 18 countries by way of international collaborations. The most productive countries of collaboration are Saudi Arabia with 42, USA with 16, France and Singapore with 6, Switzerland with 5, followed by 13 Countries which are listed in the below table 1.

Table: 1. International collaboration of Prof. Akbarsha

Country	Publications	Country	Publications
Saudi Arabia	42	Taiwan	3
United States	16	Hong Kong	2
France	6	South Korea	2
Singapore	6	Austria	1
Switzerland	5	China	1
Finland	3	Netherlands	1
Germany	3	Sri Lanka	1
Italy	3	Turkey	1
Spain	3	United Kingdom	1

Author Collaboration:

Figure 2 shows that among 184 investigated documents, 29 documents was collaborated with Dr. A. Riyasdeen (Prince Sultan Military Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia), 23 documents with Dr. M. Palaniandavar (School of Chemistry, Bharathidasan University), 20 documents with Dr. O.V. Oommen (University of Kerala, Thiruvananthapuram, India), and 18 documents with Dr. V. S. Periasamy (King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia). Majority of the co-authors are from various, Schools, Centres and Departments of Bharathidasan University.

Figure: 2. Co-authored document**Collaborator Institutions:**

Professor Akbarsha got the gain in impact due to collaborations both at national and international level Institutions (Table 2). The results depict that top institutions, which do more collaboration with institutions, get higher and positive impact out of his collaborations; overall, there is a positive impact on collaboration. With respect to collaborations, King Saud University, to which he was Visiting Professor for two years (41) stands at the first, National College, Tiruchirappalli (20), is standing at the second position, University of Kerala (20) is standing at third position, followed by Central University of Tamil Nadu (10), Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute India (9), Jamal Mohamed College, Tiruchirappalli (6), and Holy Cross

College, Tiruchirappalli

(6). The study found that the collaborations count (142) with National and International Institutions have been raised rapidly in terms of publications and Citations.

Table: 2. Institution-wise collaboration

Institution	Rec.	Institution	Rec.
King Saud University, Riyad, Saudi Arabia	41	Institute for Risk Assessment Sciences, Utrecht University, Utrecht, The Netherlands	1
National College, Tiruchirappalli, India	20	Departement Dier in Wetenschap en maatschappij, Universiteit Utrecht, The Netherlands	1
University of Kerala, Trivandrum, India	20	Faculteit Diergeneeskunde, Universiteit Utrecht, The Netherlands	1
Central University of Tamil Nadu, Tiruvarur, India	10	Institute for In Vitro Sciences, Inc., Gaithersburg, MD, USA	1
Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute, Bhavnagar, India	9	IRSEA Research Institute in Semiochemistry and Applied Ethology, France	1
Jamal Mohamed College, Tiruchirappalli, India	6	EnvisBE Solutions Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai, India	1
Holy Cross College, Tiruchirappalli, India	6	People for Ethical Treatment of Animals (PeTA) India, New Delhi, India	1
Raghunathpur College, Puralia. West Bengal, India	5	Konkuk University, Seoul, S. Korea.	1
National Centre for Biological Sciences, Bangalore, India	5	Emory University, Atlanta, Georgia, USA	1
Nanyang Technological University, Singapore	5	Universitat de Barcelona, Spain	1
University of Madras, Chennai, India	5	Universite de Neuchatel, Switserland	1
Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Mumbai	5	University of Valencia, Spain	1
Lee Kong Chian School of Medicine, Singapore	5	Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA, USA	1
Indian Institute of Technology, Mumbai, India	4	Universidad de la Laguna, Spain	1
University of Kentucky, Lexington, Kentucky, USA	4	Marshall University, West Virginia, USA	1
Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, India	4	National Taiwan University, Taipei, Taiwan	1
Dr A.L.M Postgraduate Institute of Basic Medical Sciences, University of Madras, Chennai, India	4	National Institute of Technology, Tiruchirappalli, India	1
Shibpur Dinobundhoo Institution, Howra, WB, India	4	Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education and Research, Aligarh, India	1
SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chennai, India	3	Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, MD, USA	1
Abo Akademi University, University of Turuku, Finland	3	Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Research Institute, Pondicherry, India	4
Texas A & M University, Texas, USA	3	Agharkar Research Institute, Pune, India	3
Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Switzerland	3	Bishop Heber College, Tiruchirappalli, India	1
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, India	3	Louisiana State University, Baton, Rughe, USA	1
Central University of Kerala, Kasargod, Kerala, India	3	University of Kentucky College of Medicine, Lexington, KY, USA	1
Bharath College of Science and Management, Chennai, India	2	Utrecht University, Utrecht, The Netherlands	1
In Vitro ADMET Laboratories LLC, Columbia, MD, USA.	2	Medizinische Universitat Innsbruck, Austria	1

Episkin Academy, L'Oréal Research and Innovation, Linz, France	2	Pusan National University, South Korea	1
Kerala State Biodiversity Board, Trivandrum, India	2	University of Kalyani, Kalyani, WB, India	1
Winro Science Research Foundation, Tiruchirappalli, India	2	Gebze Teknik Üniversitesi, Turkey	1
Fisk University, Nashville, Tennessee, USA	2	City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong	1
King Saud University College of Science, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia	2	Oxford Brookes University, Oxford, England	1
National Dairy Research Institute, Karnal, Haryana, India	2	National Cheng Kung University, Taipei, Taiwan	1
Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, India	2	Alagappa University, Karaikudi, India	1
Indian Institute of Science, Bengaluru, India	2	National University of Singapore, Singapore	1
Central Leather Research Institute, Chennai, India	2	Rajiv Gandhi Centre for Biotechnology, Trivandrum, India	1
Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi, India	2	Jadavpur University, Jadavpur, Kolkatta, WB, India	1
Bhabha Atomic Research Centre,	2	North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong, India	1
Homi Bhabha National Institute, Mumbai, India	2	South China Seas Institute of Oceanography, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China	1
Kalasalangam Academy of Research and Education, Krishnankoil, Srivilliputtur, India	2	University of Calcutta, Kolkatta, WB, India	1
Vivekananda Mahavidyalaya, Burdwan, WB, India.	2	Madras Christian College, Tambaram, Chennai, India	1
National Institute of Technology, Durgapur, India	2	Universität Konstanz, Konstanz, Germany	1
Indian Institute of Science Education and Research, Mohali, India	2	Veterinary College and Research Institute, Namakkal, India	1
Urumu Dhanalakshmi College, Tiruchirappalli, India	2	Turun Yliopistollinen Keskussairaala, Turuku, Finland	1
Kanchi Mamunivar Centre for Post-Graduate Studies, Pondicherry, India	1	Università degli Studi di Camerino, Italy	1
Mother Theresa Post Graduate and Research Institute of Health Sciences, Pondicherry, India	1	Université de Genève Faculté de Médecine, Switzerland	1
Ramsaday College, Amta, WB, India	1	Loyola College, Chennai, India	1
Bhatath College of Science and Management, Chennai, India	1	Institute of Science, Mumbai, India	1
Raja Serfoji Government College, Thanjavur, India	1	Turku Centre for Biotechnology, Finland	1
Doerenkamp-Zbinden Foundation, Zurich, Switzerland	1	Hindustan Unilever Limited, Bangalore, India	1
Manokaryon Bioproducts and Services, Salem, India	1	University of Oklahoma Health Sciences Center, Oklahoma, USA	1
Government College, Chittur, AP, India	1	Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy	1
Devaswom Board Pampa College, Parumala, Kerala	1	Children's Hospital, Boston, USA	1
Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing CAAT-Europe, Konstanz, Germany	1	Vector Control Research Centre India, Pondicherry, India	1
National Facility for Biopharmaceuticals, Mumbai, India	1	Università degli Studi della Tuscia Viterbo, Italy	1
National Yang-Ming University, Taiwan	1	University of Colombo, Sri Lanka	1
Universite de Neuchatel, Institut de chimie, Switzerland	1	University of Colombo Faculty of Medicine, Colombo, Sri Lanka	1
Mithibai College of Arts, Chauhan Institute of Science & Amrutben Jivanlal College of Commerce and Economics, Mumbai, India	1	A.V.V.M Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur, TN, India	1

ICAR - Central Institute of Brackishwater Aquaculture, Chennai, India	1	Narsee Monjee Institute of Management Studies, Mumbai, India	1
Anna University of Technology, Tiruchirappalli, TN, India	1	Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, Aligarh, UP, India	1
Jawaharlal Nehru Institute of Advanced Studies, Hyderabad, India	1		

Subject domain-wise distribution of Publications:

Among the subject-wise distribution of publications, the largest share (82) of publications comes from Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology, followed by Chemistry (46), Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics (40), Agricultural and Biological Sciences (39), Medicine (25), Health Professions (15), Chemical Engineering (12), Multidisciplinary (10), etc., during 1992-2020 (Fig. 3). The study found that the Professor touched several disciplines of science subjects.

Figure: 3. Subject area-wise distribution of Publications Bibliographical form-wise

distribution of Publications:

In terms of document types, 90.76% (167) appeared as Journal Articles, 5.43% (10) as Conference papers, 1.09% (2) in Book Chapters, Erratum and Review respectively, and only one publication in Editorial publication (Fig. 4).

Figure: 4. Document type-wise distribution of Publications Source title-wise distribution of

Publications:

In terms of sources, 91 titles were preferred by Professor Akbarsha for his publication at National and International levels (Table 3). 12 publications appeared in Altex (Cite Score-8.4, SNIP-1.529, SJR-1.270 and Impact Factor: 4.56) and Journal Of Morphology (Cite Score-2.7; SNIP-0.800; SJR-0.681 and Impact Factor:1.56) stand at first position, Biomedical Letters (SNIP-0.339, SJR-0.108 and Impact Factor-1.25)) and Indian Journal Of Experimental Biology (Cite Score-3.0; SNIP-0.512; SJR-0.227 and IF-1.25) stand at second position with 10 publications. The list of 10 most productive source titles along with their output is shown in the table below. According to Cite Score Human Reproduction registered with 10.1 (SNIP-2.256, SJR-2.491 and IF-5.72) is standing at first position followed by Fertility and Sterility with 9.8 Cite Score (SNIP-2.015, SJR-2.31 and IF-5.21) is standing at second position, Archives of Toxicology with 9.6 Cite Score (SNIP-1.550, SJR-1.379 and IF-5.66) is sanding at third position.

Table: 3. Source title-wise distribution of Publications

Source Title	Publications	Cite Score	SNIP	SJR
Altex	12	8.4	1.529	1.270
Journal Of Morphology	12	2.7	0.800	0.681
Biomedical Letters	10	-	0.339	0.108
Indian Journal Of Experimental Biology	10	3.0	0.512	0.227
Scientific Reports	8	7.2	1.365	1.341
Dalton Transactions	7	6.8	0.938	1.048
Journal Of Inorganic Biochemistry	7	6.0	0.926	0.63
RSC Advances	6	6.5	0.827	0.736
Food And Chemical Toxicology	4	6.7	1.353	0.902
Inorganic Chemistry	4	7.9	1.164	1.349
Cytobios	3	-	0.505	0.171
New Journal Of Chemistry	3	4.7	0.775	0.712
Phytotherapy Research	3	6.7	1.423	0.905
Polyhedron	3	3.9	0.663	0.451
Reproduction	3	5.9	1.148	1.201
Reproductive Toxicology	3	5.6	0.894	0.816
Acta Zoologica	2	2.4	0.668	0.445
Biological Structures And Morphogenesis	2	-	-	-
Fish Physiology And Biochemistry	2	3.4	0.999	0.676
Journal Of Biological Sciences	2	1.1	1.031	0.191
Journal Of Cellular Biochemistry	2	3.9	0.907	0.971
Journal Of Chemical Sciences	2	2.6	0.538	0.321
Journal Of Pharmacology And Pharmacotherapeutics	2	2.0	0.495	0.269
Journal Of Photochemistry And Photobiology B Biology	2	8.1	1.289	0.835
Reproduction In Domestic Animals	2	2.3	0.856	0.553
Zeitschrift Fur Mikroskopisch Anatomische Forschung Abteilung 2	2	-	-	-
Zoology	2	-	-	-
ACS Omega	1	2.7	0.728	0.767
Acta Physiologica Hungarica	1	-	-	-
Advanced Science Letters	1	0.4	0.316	0.126
Animal Reproduction New Research Developments	1	-	-	-
Annals Of Applied Biology	1	3.5	0.954	0.713

Anticancer Research	1	3.3	0.633	0.716
Apoptosis	1	8.0	1.115	1.127
Applied Biochemistry And Biotechnology	1	4.2	0.828	0.562
Applied Organometallic Chemistry	1	3.6	0.711	0.508
Applied Surface Science	1	8.7	1.439	1.230
Archiv Der Pharmazie	1	3.8	0.670	0.366
Archives Of Toxicology	1	9.6	1.550	1.379
Australian Journal Of Chemistry	1	2.3	0.296	0.278
Biocatalysis And Agricultural Biotechnology	1	2.8	0.986	0.506
Biochemical Pharmacology	1	7.5	1.217	1.509
Biochemistry And Biophysics Reports	1	3.6	0.853	0.635
Biology Of Reproduction	1	5.2	1.025	1.248
Biomass And Bioenergy	1	6.6	1.415	1.110
Biometals	1	4.7	0.877	0.650
Biotechnology Letters	1	4.3	0.727	0.595
Cancer Chemotherapy And Pharmacology	1	5.6	1.040	1.239
Cell And Tissue Research	1	7.1	1.106	1.402
Cell Biochemistry And Biophysics	1	3.9	0.703	0.599
Chemico Biological Interactions	1	5.9	1.181	0.896
Colloids And Surfaces B Biointerfaces	1	7.1	1.095	0.929
Comparative Biochemistry And Physiology Part C Toxicology And Pharmacology	1	4.4	0.940	0.718
Domestic Animal Endocrinology	1	4.4	0.941	0.683
Environmental Pollution	1	9.3	1.805	1.968
European Journal Of Inorganic Chemistry	1	4.5	0.676	0.693
European Journal Of Medicinal Chemistry	1	8.3	1.540	1.144
Evidence Based Complementary And Alternative Medicine	1	2.9	0.809	0.510
Fertility And Sterility	1	9.8	2.015	2.311
Future Microbiology	1	3.9	0.779	1.017
Human Reproduction	1	10.1	2.256	2.491
Indian Journal Of Chemistry Section A Inorganic Physical Theoretical And Analytical Chemistry	1	1.2	0.278	0.178
Inorganica Chimica Acta	1	3.9	0.690	0.447
Journal Of Antibiotics	1	4.3	0.862	0.559
Journal Of Basic Microbiology	1	3.4	0.809	0.611
Journal Of Biomolecular Structure And Dynamics	1	4.5	0.980	0.504
Journal Of Coordination Chemistry	1	2.7	0.500	0.291
Journal Of Ethnopharmacology	1	6.3	1.599	0.898
Journal Of Nutrition And Metabolism	1	3.1	1.172	0.637
Journal Of Reproduction And Fertility	1	-	1.687	0.676
Journal Of Zoology	1	-	-	-
Materials Letters	1	5.5	0.941	0.753
Medicinal Chemistry Research	1	3.2	0.796	0.357
Microscopy Research And Technique	1	2.8	0.903	0.469
Molecular And Cellular Biochemistry	1	5.1	0.842	0.836
Molecular Biosystems	1	6.8	1.048	0.988
Particle And Particle Systems Characterization	1	5.5	0.538	0.909
Pharmacognosy Magazine	1	2.1	0.878	0.345
Phytomedicine	1	5.7	1.502	0.958
Planta	1	5.4	1.269	1.259
Rare Animals Of India	1	-	-	-
Reproductive Biology	1	3.0	0.745	0.622

Saudi Journal Of Biological Sciences	1	4.8	1.734	0.649
Science Asia	1	0.7	0.419	0.160
Scientia Pharmaceutica	1	2.9	1.071	0.384
Spectrochimica Acta Part A Molecular And Biomolecular Spectroscopy	1	5.1	1.088	0.550
Springer Plus	1	3.4	1.476	0.409
Toxicology In Vitro	1	5.0	0.905	0.799
Zoological Science	1	1.7	0.565	0.441
Zygote	1	2.6	0.600	0.435

Most frequently occurred Keywords:

A set of main keywords and related keywords along with their research output have been identified, which throw light on the type of work undertaken in different keywords. Among the 159 main keywords, the largest number of publications (129) on Animals, followed by Human with 102, Controlled Study 54, Nonhuman 53, Male 49, Apoptosis and Metabolism with 43, Chemistry with 37, animal Experiment and DNA with 35, respectively (Table 4).

Table: 4. Keyword-wise distribution of Publications

Keywords	Occurs	Keywords	Occurs	Keywords	Occurs
Animals	129	DNA Binding	13	Circular Dichroism	7
Human	102	Animal Model	12	DNA Fragmentation	7
Controlled Study	54	Phenanthrolines	12	Diseases	7
Non-human	53	Reproductive Toxicity	12	Dose Response	7
Male	49	Cobalt	11	Dose-Response Relationship, Drug	7
Apoptosis	43	Mouse	11	Drug Synthesis	7
Metabolism	43	Tumor Cell Line	11	Epithelium Cell	7
Chemistry	37	X Ray Crystallography	11	Histopathology	7
Animal Experiment	35	Animal Testing Alternative	10	Imine	7
DNA	35	Binding Energy	10	Imines	7
Cytotoxicity	33	Caecilia	10	In Vivo Study	7
Human Cell	32	Conference Paper	10	Leydig Cell	7
Drug Effect	31	Hydrophobicity	10	Mitochondria	7
Female	30	MCF-7 Cells	10	Mitochondrial Membrane Potential	7
Rat	27	Protein Binding	10	Plant Extract	7
Unclassified Drug	27	Spermatozoon Motility	10	Rattus	7
Priority Journal	25	Toxicity Testing	10	Reactive Oxygen Metabolite	7
Cell Death	23	Calf Thymus DNA	9	Reactive Oxygen Species	7
Testis	22	Caspase 3	9	Sperm	7
Copper	21	Chemical Structure	9	Spermatozoon	7
Transmission Electron Microscopy	21	Complexation	9	Toxicity	7
Antineoplastic Agent	20	Drug Cytotoxicity	9	Antioxidants	6
Antineoplastic Agents	20	Mice	9	Binding Affinity	6
Epididymis	20	Mitochondrion	9	Breast Neoplasms	6

Cell Line, Tumor	19	Molecular Docking	9	Caecilian	6
Ligands	19	Oxidative Stress	9	Cancer Cell Culture	6
Rats	19	Pathology	9	Carbendazim	6
Ultrastructure	19	Phenanthroline Derivative	9	Cell Cycle Arrest	6
Animal Tissue	18	Sertoli Cell	9	Cell Structure	6
In Vitro Study	18	1,10-phenanthroline	8	Cells	6
Physiology	18	Caecilians	8	Chlorine Compounds	6
Spermatogenesis	18	Cancer Cell	8	Cisplatin	6
Animal Cell	17	Cattle	8	Cobalt Compounds	6
Cell Survival	17	Cell Proliferation	8	Concentration Response	6
Drug Effects	17	Cytoplasm	8	Copper Complex	6
Histology	17	Drug Screening	8	Crystal Structure	6
Ligand	17	Gene Expression Regulation	8	Drug Screening Assays, Antitumor	6
Cell Viability	16	IC50	8	Enzyme Activity	6
Comet Assay	16	Ichthyophis Tricolor	8	Gene Expression	6
DNA Cleavage	16	India	8	Genetics	6
Amphibia	15	Lizard	8	Hydrogen Bond	6
Antineoplastic Activity	15	MCF 7 Cell Line	8	IC 50	6
Cell Culture	15	Microscopy	8	Models, Molecular	6
DNA Damage	15	Platinum Compounds	8	Molecular Docking Simulation	6
Microscopy, Electron, Transmission	15	Procedures	8	Organometallic Compounds	6
Coordination Compound	14	Protein Bcl 2	8	Ruthenium Compounds	6
Gymnophiona	14	Protein Expression	8	Scanning Electron Microscopy	6
Rats, Wistar	14	Spermatozoa	8	Sperm Motility	6
Synthesis	14	Absorption Spectroscopy	7	Synthesis (chemical)	6
Vincristine	14	Animalia	7		
Cell Nucleus	13	Antiproliferative Activity	7		
Coordination Complexes	13	Binding Site	7		
Cytology	13	Uraeotyphlus narayani	6		

Funding Sponsors:

Collaboration in research can improve project outcomes and communication. 32 research funding agencies have supported National and International collaborations (Table 5). While research funds greatly determine the success of scientists, it is not always easy to find sources of funding. To help researchers in the search for project grants, we have made a list of more than 30 funding agencies that provide grants for international collaboration. It is evident from the below table that University Grants Commission 32 is emerging as top funding agency, followed by Department of Science and Technology, Ministry of Science and Technology, India for 19 research activities, Department of Science and Technology, Government of Kerala for 15 publications. Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (11). It can be concluded with below analysis that UGC and DST supported most of his research.

Table: 5. Funding agency wise distribution of Publications

Funding Agency	Rec.	Funding Agency	Rec.
University Grants Commission	32	Ministry of Education - Singapore	2
Department of Science and Technology, Ministry of Science and Technology, India	19	Academy of Finland	1
Department of Science and Technology, Government of Kerala	15	Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council	1
Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research	11	CLRI Chennai	1
SAP North America	5	Chonbuk National University	1
Science and Engineering Research Board	5	Connecticut State Emergency Response Commission	1
Lee Kong Chian School of Medicine, Nanyang Technological University	4	Council of Scientific and Industrial Research	1
CSIR, India	3	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft	1
DBT, Government of West Bengal	3	Fondation de Coopération Scientifique Campus Paris-Saclay	1
Indian National Science Academy	3	Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología	1
King Saud University	3	National Research Foundation of Korea	1
Bhabha Atomic Research Centre	2	Sigrid Juséliuksen Säätiö	1
Indian Council of Agricultural Research	3	University of Madras	1
Indian Council of Medical Research	2	Åbo Akademi	1
Kerala State Council for Science, Technology and Environment	2		

Highly Cited papers:

The 24 top high cited papers (listed in the table 6) have received citations 4366 (since their publication till 2020). These 7 papers together have received 1313 citations, registered an average citation per paper of 187.54. 24 papers have received 2484 citations and registered an average citation per paper 103.5. 24 publications are registered with more than 50 Citations at Global level. With respect to Citations count, paper entitled “Mixed-ligand copper(II)- phenolate complexes: Effect of coligand on enhanced DNA and protein binding, DNA cleavage, and anticancer activity, Inorganic Chemistry, Volume 46, Issue 20, 1 October 2007, Pages 8208-8221” stands at the first with 447 Citations, Internationally collaborated (Institut de Chimie, Université de Neuchâtel, Avenue de Bellevaux 51, CH-2007 Neuchâtel, Switzerland), Nationally (National Centre for Biological Science, Tata Institute for Fundamental Research, Bangalore 560 065, India) collaborated paper. Citation benchmarking-97th percentile shows how citations received by this document compare with the average for similar documents and Field-Weighted Citation Impact is 5.29 shows how well this document is cited when compared to similar documents. A value greater than 1.00 means the document is more cited than expected. *Followed by paper entitle* “Induction of cell death by ternary copper(II) complexes of l-tyrosine and diimines: Role of coligands on DNA binding and cleavage and anticancer activity, Inorganic Chemistry, Volume 48, Issue 4, 16 February 2009, Pages 1309-1322” stands at the second position with 201 citations. Citation benchmarking-97th percentile and Field-Weighted Citation Impact is 5.22.

Figure: 5. PlumX Metrics analysis used to evaluate the highly cited paper

Further, PlumX analytics shows the top highly cited paper (446) of Rajendiran et al (2007) had been published in Inorganic Chemistry (IF: 4.825) (Fig. 5). This indicates that publishing article in the high impact factor (IF) journal is one of the major factors with respect to get more citation. PlumX metrics is providing insights into the scholarly significance with individual pieces of research output.

Table: 6. The highly cited papers

S.No	Documents	Citations	<2016	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Sub total	>2020	Total
1	Mixed-ligand copper(II)-phenolate complexes: Effect of colig...	2007	243	46	42	38	47	31	204		446
2	Induction of cell death by ternary copper(II) complexes of l...	2009	109	20	25	17	22	8	92		201
3	Mixed ligand copper(II) complexes of N, N-bis(benzimidazol-2...	2012	59	20	18	19	20	18	95	1	155
4	Ternary dinuclear copper(II) complexes of a hydroxybenzamide...	2011	62	14	13	20	18	17	82		144
5	Non-covalent DNA binding and cytotoxicity of certain mixed-l...	2008	80	13	13	9	12	4	51	1	132
6	New ruthenium(II) arene complexes of anthracenyl-appended di...	2014	15	26	20	19	22	15	102		117
7	Influence of nutrient deprivations on lipid accumulation in ...	2012	46	16	12	14	14	14	70	1	117
8	Efficient DNA cleavage mediated by mononuclear mixed ligand ...	2012	46	12	11	9	7	7	46		92
9	Anticancer mechanism of plumbagin, a	2008	50	12	11	9	6	3	41		91

	natural compound, on no...										
10	Chronic chromium exposure-induced changes in testicular hist...	2005	50	9	6	7	3	5	30		80
11	Surfactant-cobalt(III) complexes: Synthesis, critical micell...	2009	46	11	6	4	5	5	31		77
12	Copper(ii) complexes with 2NO and 3N donor ligands: Synthesi...	2013	27	10	8	12	13	5	48		75
13	Interaction of mixed ligand copper(II) complexes with CT DNA...	2013	21	17	10	8	8	7	50	1	72
14	A trinuclear zinc-Schiff base complex: Biocatalytic activity...	2014	8	13	19	12	10	7	61		69
15	Interaction of rac-[M(diimine) ₃] ²⁺ (M ...	2011	32	5	12	6	7	7	37		69
16	Antifertility effect of Andrographis paniculata (Nees) in ma...	1990	61	1	2	1	1	1	6		67
17	Mixed ligand copper(II) complexes of 1,10-phenanthroline wit...	2014	10	7	11	12	15	11	56		66
18	Spermatotoxic effect of aflatoxin B ₁ in the albin...	2003	44	3	2	4	8	5	22		66
19	Mixed ligand μ -phenoxo-bridged dinuclear copper(ii) complexe...	2014	12	11	9	10	11	10	51		63
20	Aspects of the male reproductive toxicity/male antifertility...	2000	43	4	6	2	4	3	19		62
21	Synthesis and characterization of nano-hydroxyapatite at amb...	2009	37	2	5	7	3	5	22		59
22	DNA binding, prominent DNA cleavage and efficient anticancer...	2011	34	6	4	9	2	3	24		58
23	Hepatotoxic effect of ochratoxin A and citrinin, alone and i...	2015	2	8	10	8	14	11	51		53
24	Mixed ligand copper(II) complexes of 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phena...	2014	9	13	5	6	8	11	43		52
	Total		1986	461	477	476	512	445	2371	9	4366

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

Professor Akbarsha has contributed 184 publications in Life Sciences and other subject domains during 1992-2020, registered 4366 citations and average Citation per Article is 23.73. The most productive countries of collaboration are Saudi Arabia (42), USA with 16, France and Singapore with 6 each, Switzerland with 5, followed by 13 Countries. According to Cite Score Human Reproduction registered with 10.1 (SNIP-2.256, SJR-2.491 and IF-5.72)

is standing at first position followed by Fertility and Sterility with 9.8 Cite Score (SNIP-2.015, SJR-2.31 and IF-5.21) is standing at second position, Archives of Toxicology with 9.6 Cite Score (SNIP-1.550, SJR-1.379 and IF-5.66) is standing at third position. The study found that the collaborations count (142) with National and International Institutions have raised rapidly in terms of publications and citations.

We conclude that scientometrics plays an important role in the dissemination of a particular scientist whose interest lies in the number of important papers he or she have published. In the above case study, Prof. Mohammad Abdulkader Akbarsha has truly advanced our understanding in subjects dealing with Life Sciences. Citing the number of publications, citations and collaboration details reveal the enormous interest the author has taken to reach his goal as of now. There is no dearth of ideal role model scientists in India. What we lack is a systematic and continuous study on such scientists. Hence, the comment “Most of the developing countries lack local “role models” to motivate other scientists does not hold good at least for India.

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